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A REVIEW OF ANALYTICAL PERSPECTIVES OF LINAGLIPTIN

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ABSTRACT

Linagliptin is an oral anti-diabetic drug belong to the class of dipeptidyl peptidase -4 (DPP-4 inhibitors). It is widely used in the treatment of type -II diabetes mellitus which is characterized by insulin resistance in peripheral tissue and insulin secretory defect of the β - cells. Linagliptin is been approved by the US food & Drug administration for the management of type -II diabetes. This work aims to compiling the published analytical methods referred so far in the literature in the determination of linagliptin in the biological samples and pharmaceutical formulations. Techniques like HPLC, UV & MASS spectroscopy, EI - Tandem Mass spectrometry, pharmacokinetic studies & spectrophotometric methods have been utilized so far in the analysis, from which we can see HPLC methods have been operated most extensively in various analytical perspectives. Based on the findings of the present review, linagliptin is widely used as an treatment adjunctive to a regimen of an insulin secretagogue.

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INTRODUCTION

Linagliptin { 1 H - (Purine-2,6 dione, 8- (3R) - 3- amino -1- Piperdiny) -7 -(2- butyn -1-yl) -3,7 dihydro - 3-methyl - 1 - (4 methyl -2- quinazoliny) Methyl} is a DPP-4 inhibitors in the treatment of type -II diabetes, DPP-4 (Dipeptidyl peptidase -4) is an enzyme that degrades the hormones, glucagon like peptides -1 (GLP-1) and glucose dependent insulin tropic polypeptide (GIP). Both GLP-1 & GIP increases the insulin biosynthesis and secretion from pancreatic α -Cells resulting in the reduction of hepatic glucose output [1]. Linagliptin is indicated as adjuvant to diet and exercise to improve glycemic control in patients with diabetes -II [2]. Various techniques have been reported in the determination of linagliptin in the pharmaceutical dosage forms. The objective of review article is to understand the various simple accurate RP-HPLC methods with short retention time (migration time) and various methods to validate the newly developed method as per the ICH guidelines [3]. In the present review, we have compiled the published analytical methods reported so far in the determination of linagliptin in pharmaceutical and biological samples. Techniques like spectrophotometry, HPLC, LCMS, LC-ESI-MS where have been used for analysis, from which HPLC methods were been extensively adopted.

Fig.1 Structure of linagliptin.

Fig.2 Overview of analytical methods for estimation of a linagliptin in pharmaceutical and biological samples

Sample preparation strategies

Sample preparation is an integral part of analytical methodology and it was reported that approximately 30 % error is contributed from sample analysis was due to sample preparation [6]. The various diluents utilized for analysis of linagliptin are 0.02M phosphate buffer (p^H 5.5), acetonitrile, methanol. In major cases, methanol was used as a diluent. The sample preparation techniques for the extraction of linagliptin from biological matrices like serum, plasma and urine include liquid -liquid extraction with diethyl ether, N-butyl ether & ethyl acetate and protein precipitated with methanol.

Analytical methods

Spectrophotometry:

In the literature, twenty simple, accurate, zero order, first derivative spectrophotometric methods have been developed [7] out of which four methods were for determination of linagliptin alone, where as remaining are quantifying linagliptin in combination with other drug substances.

Table :1 Representative spectroscopical method analysis of linagliptin.

S.NO	Compound	Method	λ_{max}	Solvent	LOD	Reference
1.	Linagliptin	Spectrophotometric	299	Methanol	0.247	[8]
2.	Linagliptin	Spectrophotometric	294	Methanol & Water	0.246	[9]

Chromatography:**Biological samples:**

Rutvik H pandya *et.al* [10] developed a method in human plasma by using simultaneous method for estimation of linagliptin and metformin in combined dosage form. The mobile phase used in this method was a mixture of acetonitrile and 0.01 M diphosphate buffer adjusting the p^H 7.0 with orthophosphoric acid (75:25v/v). Phenformin was used as a internal standard for this method. The method has been validated as per the ICH guide lines such as long term stability studies, LLOQ, LQC, MQC & HQC concentration levels were found to be 9.823,1.983,1.325 & 2.715 respectively.

Pharmaceutical samples:

Analytical methods for the determination of linagliptin in the pharmaceutical dosage form using HPLC [11-20]

Table :2 Reported analytical HPLC methods for determination of linagliptin in combination with other drugs like metformin in pharmaceutical dosage forms.

S.No	Aim of study	Mobile phase	Column	Detection	λ max (nm)	Flow rate	LOD $\mu\text{g/mL}$	reference
1.	Validated RP-HPLC method for the determination of linagliptin	Methanol : Water (83:17v/v)	Gemini C18 column (250x4.6mm, I.D, 5 μm)	UV	241	1mL/min	2.5	[11]
2.	Simultaneous estimation of metformin and linagliptin in tablet dosage forms	Acetonitrile : 0.2M Phosphate Buffer (35:65 v/v)	Waters X-bridge C18 column (4.6X150mm ID, 5 μm)	UV	225	1mL/min	2.6	[12]
3.	Simultaneous estimation and stability indicating study of Metformin and linagliptin in dosage forms	Phosphate buffer : acetonitrile (60:40)	Inertsil ODS - 3V C18 column (250X4.6mm ID, 5 μm)	PDA	280	1mL/min	2.7	[13]
4.	Development and validation of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of linagliptin and metformin	Acetonitrile : Water : Methanol (25:20:25 v/v)	BDS hypersil C8 column (250x4.6mm ID, 5 μm)	PDA	243	1mL/min	0.89	[14]
5.	Validated RP-HPLC method for the determination of linagliptin	Methanol : Water (83:17 v/v)	Gemini C18 column (250x4.6mm ID, 5 μm)	UV	241	1mL/min	0.025	[15]
6.	Determination of Metformin hydrochloride and linagliptin by RP-HPLC in bulk and Pharmaceutical formulation	Phosphate buffer : Methanol : acetonitrile (65:10:25v/v)	Phenomex luna RP-18 reverse phase C18 column (150x4.6mm ID, 5 μm)	UV	231	1mL/min	3.08	[16]
7.	Stability indicating liquid chromatographic method for simultaneous assay of linagliptin and metformin pure and tablet dosage form	Phosphate buffer : acetonitrile (40:60v/v)	Zorbax CV18 column (250X4.6mm ID, 5 μm)	PDA	236	1mL/min	0.673	[17]
8.	Simultaneous determination of linagliptin and metformin by RP-HPLC method	Methanol : 0.05M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate (70:30v/v)	Lichrosphere 100 RP -18e (125x4mm ID, 5 μm)	PDA	267	0.6mL/m in	0.07591	[18]
9.	Simultaneous determination of metformin	Dihydrogen	Chromolith C18	UV	208	2.5mL/m in	0.02	[19]

	and 3 gliptins in pharmaceutical formulations using RP-HPLC	Phosphate : (50x4.6mm acetonitrile ID, 5µm) (60:40v/v)							
10.	Development and validation of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of empagliflozin and linagliptin in tablet formulation	0.1% perchloric acid : acetonitrile (60:40)	BDS column (250X4.6mm ID, 5µm)	C18	UV	230	1mL/min	0.43µg/mL	[20]

LC - MS/MS

Swetha parsha *et.al* [21] for the determination of the key impurities in linagliptin pramipexole. The liquid chromatograph was carried out in a diode array detector and the control analyst were been performed on Bruker avance 400 MHZ instrument under the control of topspin software. Linagliptin key impurity showed the peak at RT 26.4 min and the protonated molecular ion ($M^+ + H$) at $m/z = 957$. The corresponding molecular formula $C_{51}H_{56}N_{16}O_4$ suggesting that two molecules of linagliptin connected through methylene group.

UPLC

Nidhi Dubey *et.al* [22] studied a simple, precise and accurate isocratic RP-UPLC method for the determination of linagliptin in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation. An Isocratic separation has been achieved on an agilent SB -C18 RRHD (50X2.1mm ID, 1.8µm) column using mobile phase of 0.01M potassium phosphate p^H 4.0 and acetonitrile (30:70v/v) at a flow rate of 3mL/min. The injection volume is 2µL and the detection has been carried out at 292 nm using PDA detector. The method has been validated as per ICH guidelines for specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness and ruggedness. The method is linear in the drug concentration range of 2.5-100µg/mL with co-relation coefficient of 0.9998. The proposed method is more sensitive and selective and short analysis of time. The LOD and LOQ value represents of 0.25µg/mL and 0.5µg/mL.

Bioanalytical studies

Mohammad Al bratty *et.al* [23] developed a liquid chromatography associated with tandem mass spectrophotometric method for the simultaneous estimation of metformin hydrochloride, linagliptin, sitagliptin and vildagliptin from human plasma. The developed method was validated as per the ICH guide lines. Chromatographic separations were achieved using chromolith high resolution RP 18 HPLC column (100x4.6mm, 1.15µm) in an isocratic elution using the mobile phase composed of 0.01M ammonium formate buffer : acetonitrile (80:20v/v). The flow rate is 0.4mL/min and was maintained through out the analysis. The detection was performed by triple quadrapole MS fitted with ESI probe functioning in the positive ion of MRM mode. Extraction from all drugs from plasma followed by acetonitrile crash technique. Alogliptin was used as a internal standard to minimize the error during analysis. The LOD where 1.76,1.94,0.17,3.08ng/mL. The developed method is robust and can be applied for monitoring plasma levels of analyzed anti-diabetic drugs in preclinical and clinical pharmacokinetic studies.

On the other hand, Anna guminiczek and Anna bereckle [24] represents a review of analytical methods of the new oral drugs for the treatment of type -II diabetes focusing on DPP-4 inhibitors (gliptins) in the human plasma. The review represents the analytical procedures in the determination of drugs in the biological samples including HPLC -UV, HPLC -MS, HPTLC, CE-MS & electrochemical methods with isotopically labeled internal standards are analysed.

HPTLC

Eman I elkimary *et.al* [25] developed a HPTLC method for the determination of linagliptin, saxagliptin and vildagliptin in the binary mixtures with metformin in pharmaceutical preparations using mobile phase system (Methanol : 0.5% aqueous ammonium sulphate 8:2 v/v). Separation was carried out on HPTLC sheet of silica gel 60 F254 and the spots were measured densitometrically at 225nm for linagliptin and metformin mixture and 208 nm for saxagliptin and metformin mixture. The linear regression analysis data were used for the regression line in the range of 0.05-0.5µg/mL for linagliptin. The method was validated and showed good performances in terms of linearity LOD, LOQ, precision, accuracy selectivity and specificity. The developed method was satisfactorily applied for the analysis of pharmaceutical preparations and proved to be specific and accurate quality control on the sited drugs in the dosage forms.

Challenges

As discussed earlier, linagliptin belongs to the class of 2 BCS classification which possess high permeability and low solubility. Hence the solubility of linagliptin in water is less and it is a problem in selecting the diluents for the analysis. From the degradation studies, it was observed that treatment on strong acidic and strong basic will create a difference in the retention time. In similar lines spectrophotometric determination, multi dosage forms with complexity in to the presence of multiple entities and excipients which may cause considerable challenge to the analytical chemist in the development of analytical procedure. Due to the prevailing lacuna, it is difficult to estimate the individual drugs in the multi component dosage form. Hence routine spectrometric and chemometric methods were been preferred as an alternate resources.

CONCLUSION

There are a wide range of analytical techniques were available for the analysis of linagliptin in pharmaceutical and biological samples. The published data it was revealed that HPLC method was extensively used for the estimation of linagliptin in various matrices like plasma and serum. HPLC MS/MS method is also recommended in the determination of linagliptin in biological samples because HPLC separation ability with MS sensitivity and selectivity allows the unambiguous identification of linagliptin and its metabolites. HPLC with UV detection is applicable in the case of analysis of linagliptin in pharmaceuticals which provide us cost effective accurate method when compare with more advance techniques. In the near future, the combinations of linagliptin and metformin combinations were been available in the market, various bioanalytical method development and validation has been performed in order to study the bioavailability and bioequivalence of the drug which would help the chemists/analyses to formulate a stabilized drug.

Conflict of Interest

The authors state there is no conflict of interest

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